

A PROTOTYPE RESEARCH LABORATORY FOR AUTOMATED FABRICATION OF HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A new NASA facility has been built which has proved to be a valuable asset for obtaining data, experience, and insights for developing new and improved high performance composite processing technology. The facility consists of an ABB robot armed with a modified heated head capable of hot gas and focused infrared heating. Techniques were developed for fabricating the dry material forms required to successfully place high quality thermoplastic and thermoset composite materials. A variety of composites have been fabricated by heated head tow and tape placement and key properties obtained which demonstrate values close to those obtained by hand lay-up/autoclave processing. Future work is directed toward developing processes to fabricate net shape composites by non-autoclave ply-by-ply, cure-on-the-fly techniques.

KEYWORDS: fiber placement, in-situ cure, robot, thermoplastics, polyimides, cure-on-the-fly, non-autoclave processes, automation

INTRODUCTION

Automated robotic placement of tow, ribbon, and tape has emerged as a powerful technique for fabrication of high performance fiber-reinforced composite structure. Production-ready equipment controlled by sophisticated computer software has been used to manufacture major portions of the Boeing 777 empennage, F18EF stabilator and inlet ducts, and V22 parts, among others. However, to advance and expand low cost manufacturing, research on fiber placement technology requires access to more economical, small-scale, experimental equipment that simulates the performance of the large manufacturing facilities that are unavailable to many universities, small businesses, and research organizations. Such equipment could be used to screen and develop composite fabrication techniques utilizing new resins, new fibers, new intermediate materials forms, new in-situ curing mechanisms, net shape placement, elevated temperature applications, and metal-PMC hybrids, to name several future thrust areas.

FACILITY

NASA Langley Research Center has developed a research laboratory for automated fabrication that provides the means to address some of these research areas. The lab centers around a robotic work cell configured for fiber placement which contains an Asea Brown Boveri (ABB) robotic arm with a modified Automated Dynamics Corporation (ADC) fiber placement head and supporting software developed by ADC and Composite Machinery Company (Fig. 1) [1]. A portion of the initial work had to do with the development of placement heads, essentially stand alone end effectors that feed, heat, cut, place and laminate unidirectional fibrous material (Fig. 2) [2].

Fig. 1: NASA Langley Robotic Composite Fabrication Facility

The ABB robot can handle a payload of up to 150-kg force and has a maximum reach of 2.4 meters. The modified ADC head is capable of placing five 0.635 cm-wide ribbons or one 3.18 cm-wide tape, either thermoplastic or thermoset, although it can be modified to handle narrower tow. Several heading methods are employed including two conventional nitrogen gas torches and one recently developed focused infrared lamp. A steel compaction roller is employed (in lieu of a high temperature conformable roller) to apply pressure to the heated tape. Both a heated flat tool and a cylindrical tool on an ADC spindle satisfy most of the research requirements [2].

The focused infrared lamp was developed first to augment and later to replace the nitrogen gas torches which had serious problems with reduced heat transfer in the nip region due to hot gas flow stagnation. The radiant heat source permitted operation at lower compaction roller temperatures that reduced resin adherence to the rollers and improved part surface smoothness. Photomicrographs of thermoplastic panels placed with the infrared heater indicated low void content and good ply-ply interfacial adhesion as demonstrated by wedge peel and double cantilever beam (DCB) tests which are discussed more fully in the next Section.

Fig. 2: Schematic of the NASA Heated Head

The DCB initiation fracture toughness numbers were comparable to those reported for autoclave processed panels [3].

Facilities were also installed to study magnetic induction welding to fabricate titanium-graphite (TiGr) composites; an ideal material for fabrication by in-situ automated placement. Composite specimens were joined using a modified toroid or U-shaped magnet rather than a conventional pancake-type flattened coil magnet, the surface-treated, primed titanium foil serving as the susceptor. Frequencies from 50 to 500 kHz and power input levels from 1.25 to 1.75 kW were employed. Wedge peel tests were used to determine the strength of the titanium-graphite and graphite-graphite bonds. Good wetting and maximum peel strengths were obtained for PIXA/IM7 and PETI-5/IM7 polyimide/graphite TiGr composites at weld times of 5-10 seconds above 300°C and a spike heating temperature of 600°C for less than a second. Up to 5 plies of carbon-fiber-reinforced prepreg could be placed between titanium layers at reasonable placement rates [4]. Preliminary designs for a prototype toroid production heater to be used on the NASA robot have been made.

PLACEMENT QUALITY RIBBON AND TAPE

Technology for fabrication of a fully consolidated, dry unidirectional composite tape was developed at NASA and at several industrial locations. The NASA process involved the preparation of powder-coated towpreg using a gravity-fed powder curtain process. The towpreg is passed through a tube furnace and onto air-cooled nip rollers to convert it to a dry, fully wet-out unitape [5]. A recent modification of this process starts with “wet” towpreg or tape prepared by coating fiber with an N-methylpyrrolidone solution of the polymer and drying to 12 percent volatiles. The remaining volatiles (solvent and reaction products, if any) are removed in the tube furnace [6].

The specifications for dry ribbon and tape are shown in Table 1 [7]. Tight equipment tolerances and proper resin melt flow as well as many other factors are required to achieve tape with these specifications.

Table 1: Dry tape and ribbon requirements

Width:	0.635 +/- 0.0254 cm (ribbon) 7.62 +/- 0.0254 cm (tape)
Nominal Thickness:	0.015 cm
Thickness Variation:	Less than 25% of total thickness
Resin Content:	35 +/- 5% by weight
Void Volume:	Less than 3% (when measured by “The Water Immersion Method for Determination of Void Content of Thermoplastic Fiber Impregnated Tow”.)
Tensile Strength:	Measure and report only (ribbon only)
Product shape:	Rectangular cross-section (when inspected by photo micrograph)
Tow Splits:	Less than 0.076 cm wide, less than 7.62 cm long
Tow Alignment:	Less than 0.076 cm deviation in any linear foot
Residual Solvent:	Less than 0.01%

The most important characteristic of a good quality dry material form is its ability to be robotically placed in a rapid manner ply-by-ply and achieve consolidation with the previously laid ply. During the lay-down process, resin melt flow must be adequate to wet all the filaments in the tow and achieve intimate contact, reptation bonding and healing with the previously laid ply. To accomplish this, placement is conducted at temperatures that correspond to a minimum in the melt viscosity, yet are below polymer thermal decomposition.

The standard method for measuring the interlaminar bond quality is the DCB test. This test requires a specimen thickness of between 3-5 millimeters which translates to 24-40 plies; further, specimen preparation and testing is time consuming. A rapid screening test, the wedge peel test, was developed which required a 2-ply-thick specimen and could be tested immediately [8]. A schematic of this test is shown in Fig. 3. Correlation between the two tests was made so that the wedge peel test could be used to screen candidate ribbons and tapes for in-situ processability as well as help identify process windows and conditions for efficient placement. Typical wedge peel data is shown in Fig. 4.

A study was conducted jointly with Cytec-Fiberite in which PIXA thermoplastic polyimide ribbon was prepared under conditions that yielded material with varying degrees of processability [7]. Laminates were fabricated at the lower and upper temperature extremes of the placement processing window using automated placement equipment both at Langley and at an industrial facility. DCB and wedge peel tests were used to determine the quality of the laminates and especially the interlaminar bond formed during the placement process.

Figure 3: Schematic of wedge peel test

Fig. 4: Typical wedge peel data showing average peel force value

Ribbon made under conditions expected to be non-optimal (overheated) resulted in poor placeability and composites with weak interlaminar bond strengths, regardless of placement conditions. Ribbon made under conditions expected to be ideal showed good processability and produced well-consolidated laminates. Results were consistent from machine to machine and demonstrated the importance of ribbon quality in heated-head placement of dry material forms.

DEVELOPMENTAL ACTIVITIES

Composite Fabrication/Testing. In-situ consolidated laminates have been prepared from high temperature polyimides such as AURUM™ PIXA/IM7, AURUM™ PIXA-M/IM7 and LARC™ PETI-5/IM7 and polyarylene ethers and sulfides such as APC-2™ (PEEK)/AS4, APC-2™ (PEEK)/IM6, PEKK/AS4 and PPS/AS4 [1]. It should be noted that lightly cross-linked material such as the LARC™ PETI-5/IM7 polyimide required a high temperature postcure to optimize performance. Open hole compression strengths at room temperature of some 24-ply PEEK, PIXA, and PETI-5 quasi-isotropic panels made by ATP on large industrial equipment are given in Table 2 and compared with properties obtained from panels made by hand lay-up/autoclave procedures. The ATP panels exhibited from 85 to 104 percent of the properties of composites made by hand lay-up/autoclave. These results indicate that heated head ATP technology can be used to effectively fabricate quality high performance composite materials.

Table 2. Open Hole Compression Strengths of Quasi-isotropic Composites

Process	APC-2™ (PEEK/AS4)	APC-2™ (PEEK/IM6)	AURUM™ PIXA/IM7	LaRC PETI-5/ IM7
Hand Lay-up/Autoclave (ksi)	47	46	46	47
Adv. Tow Placement (ksi)	40	43	39	49 (autoclave cure)
% Retention	85	93	85	104

Adhesive Bonding of Thermoplastic Ribbon During Placement. High placement temperatures and pressures needed for thermoplastic require heavy expensive tooling and slow placement speeds. To lower these placement parameters, ribbon was fabricated with a thin adhesive layer coated to the placement surface. The presence of this adhesive layer permitted placement at lower temperatures while retaining interlaminar wedge peel strength [9]. The dilemma is that the adhesive film with a T_g lower than that of the composite reduces the high temperature properties of the composite.

Fig. 5: Heated Head Tape-Placed APC-2 Cylinder

Placement of Thermoplastic Cylinder Using Focused IR Heated Head. Fiber placement with the focused infrared heated head was used to fabricate a high quality well consolidated 61 cm-diameter, 91cm-long PEEK /AS4 (APC-2) graphite composite cylinder. The cylinder had an 8-ply quasi-isotropic lay-up (+45/-45/0/90/90/0/-45/+45) [10]. A photograph of the cylinder is shown in Fig. 5. Roller sticking, a primary problem in earlier work with the gas torches, was eliminated because the roller could be operated at lower temperatures. Steel compaction rollers were machined to match the curvature of the cylinder for 0°, 45° and 90° placement. Photomicrographs of the cylinder wall cross-section indicated very good interlaminar bonding (Fig. 6). However, numerous dry, voidy and poorly wet-out areas were also observed which were present in the as-purchased tape and could not be healed during the placement process. This confirms the need to prepare good quality starting material and not depend on the lay-down process to correct material form imperfections.

Modest built-up structure, including 2m by 3m panels with 3 attached stringers and 2m by 3m sandwich panels with titanium core, have been fabricated from various polyimides using industrial ATP equipment and 7.62 cm-wide tape. These parts were made as part of a cooperative program between NASA Langley and industry to develop heated head robotic placement technology for aerospace applications.

Fig. 6: Photomicrograph of the cross-section of an as-placed 8-ply APC-2 cylinder wall

FUTURE ACTIVITIES

Future activities directed toward achieving the goal of automated fabrication of high performance composites will include:

- development of sensors for on-line part quality information and in-situ defect repair;
- automated placement of metal-composite hybrids using magnetic induction heating;
- development of conformable compactors for ply drops, ply adds, and complex geometry;
- development of non-autoclave processes for epoxy thermosets including net shape placement combined with ply-by-ply, cure-on-the-fly.

In pursuit of the latter, modified resins are being investigated with new cure mechanisms such as electron beam radiation and low temperature thermal pulses. These resins have to be tailored for rapid, automated fabrication and their cure mechanisms understood and modeled. The “ultimate goal” for composite manufacture is to reproducibly and economically fabricate high quality parts that have the proper dimensions and performance properties for a selected design end use. Automation will be part of the answer as will non-autoclavability. Robotic

laboratories such as described in this paper are needed by researchers to create, study and optimize prototype processes. These labs should be flexible and broadly adaptable to screen a variety of new approaches as well as to develop and investigate new constituent materials, material forms, and cure mechanisms. Transfer of the best technology from such laboratories to industrial partners for scale-up and further tailoring should be relatively easy and efficient and will make the road to the “ultimate goal” smoother and shorter.

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